

INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF PHARMACEUTICAL RESEARCH

“A STUDY TO IDENTIFY, ASSESS AND EVALUATE THE INCIDENCE OF INTENTIONAL AND UNINTENTIONAL ORGANOPHOSPHOROUS POISONING IN A SOUTH INDIAN TERTIARY CARE TEACHING HOSPITAL AT DAVANGERE, KARNATAKA”

ARTICLE INFO

Article history

Received xxx
Available online
xxx

Keywords

Poisoning,
Suicide,
Organophosphorous
Compounds.

ABSTRACT

Poison is an object of aversion and abhorrence. The prospective observational open labelled study was enrapt to identify, evaluate and assess the incidences of intentional and unintentional organophosphorous poisoning and to assess the relation between demographic factors and organophosphorous poisoning. At the initial phase we identified the type of organophosphorous poisoning then, as per the criteria, we designed a data collection form with specified inclusion and exclusion criteria. We also identified the relation between the demographic factors and poisoning. A total number of 100 cases were collected. Based on our analysis cypermethrin+chlorpyrifos 23% (n=23) was the most commonly consumed organophosphorous compound. On age wise 20-29 years were more prone for poisoning 24% (n=24). Males outnumbered 66% (n=66) females 34% (n=34). Based on economic study low socio economic peoples 50% (n=50) were more prone to poisoning. People from rural area 90% (n=9) accounted for more poisoning cases. Incidence of poisoning were more in married subjects 57% (n=57). On occupational basis students 31% (n=31) were more prone for poisoning. Most of the cases 89% (n=89) were suicidal in nature. Most of the poisoning cases were seen among students. This study describes the importance of patient counselling and essentiality of poison information center in hospitals. Our study also emphasizes that both PIC and patient counselling are the most important vital sectors to be concentrated by the clinical pharmacists.

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Please cite this article in press as **Annmary Pious et al.** “A Study to Identify, Assess and Evaluate the Incidence of Intentional and Unintentional Organophosphorous Poisoning in A South Indian Tertiary Care Teaching Hospital at Davangere, Karnataka”. *Indo American Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*.2017;7(11).

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INTRODUCTION

Poison is an object of aversion and abhorrence. Poisons are subtle and silent weapons, which can be easily used without violence and often without arousing suspicion. As per the reports submitted by WHO, globally more than 3million of acute poisoning cases with 2,20,000 deaths occur annually. The WHO estimated that there were 873,000 suicides worldwide in 2002 which concludes, suicide a major cause of premature mortality globally. Poisoning is identified as 4th main cause of death. Acute pesticide poisoning is one of the most common causes of intentional deaths worldwide. The most commonly abused substance in India is Organophosphorous compound. Pesticide poisoning is a significant problem in India. Since India is an agrarian country in which about 60-80% of rural population solely depends on agriculture. Pesticides are routinely used for advanced farming and are readily available over the counter. Therefore, a pesticide is an easy accessing source for suicidal purpose. Studies have revealed that pesticides are the commonly abused agents for intentional poisoning. Pesticide poisoning is a major clinical problem in many parts of the world probably killing about 300,000 people every year. The toxic effect of a substance depends on the amount one is exposed to. "My life is precious and you are not allowed to hurt me so not even a small pint of poison should harm any valuable life". So as clinical pharmacists we selected this topic in order to identify, assess and evaluate the incidence of intentional and unintentional organophosphorous poisoning in a south Indian tertiary care teaching hospital, To assess the quality of management and subsequent outcomes from organophosphorous poisoning in a tertiary care teaching hospital, to assess the relationship between demographic factors and organophosphorous poisoning, to know the magnitude and pattern of acute poisoning with OP as it is important for early diagnosis, treatment and for preventive measures. [1], [2], [3], [5], [13], [15]

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Materials used:

- Inform Consent Form
- Information Leaflet
- Patient Data Collection Form
- Patient Interview Form

Study Site:

The study was conducted at Emergency, ICU Medicine and Pediatric departments of SSIMS and RC, Davangere.

Study Design:

The study was an Observational Prospective Open Labelled Study.

Study Period and Duration:

The study was carried out for a period of six months from September 2016 to February 2017.

ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS:

The study was approved by the Institutional Ethical Committee of Bapuji Pharmacy College, Davangere.

Procedure:

All OP poison ingested patients in ICU, Emergency, Medicine and Pediatrics were enrolled based on well-developed inclusion and exclusion criteria

Inclusion Criteria:

All OP compound ingested patients in ICU, Emergency, Medicine and Pediatrics of a tertiary care hospital. Patients with comorbidities like malignancies, COPD, DM and HTN were included.

Exclusion Criteria:

All pregnant ladies and patients in comatose.

Data Analysis:

The data were collected using a well-designed proforma and was analyzed using Microsoft Excel 2010.

RESULTS

Table 1: Gender distribution of poisoning cases.

SL.NO	Gender	No. Of Patients (n=100)	Percentage (%)
1	Males	66	66
2	Females	34	34

The majority of patients were males 66% (n=66) and 34% (n=34) were females.

Table 2: Socio-economic status of the patients.

SL.NO	Socio-economic status	No. of patients (n=100)	Percentage (%)
1	Low	50	50
2	Medium	36	36
3	High	14	14

Persons of low socio-economic status were involved maximum 50% (n=50) followed by medium socio-economic status 36% (n=36) and the least with high socio-economic status 14% (n=14).

Table 3: Age-wise Distribution of patients.

SL.NO	Age in years	Number of patients(n=100)	Percentage (%)
1	0-9	3	3
2	10-19	10	10
3	20-29	24	24
4	30-39	22	22
5	40-49	15	15
6	50-59	15	15
7	60-69	8	8
8	70-79	3	3

The age of patients varied from 1-79 years. OP poisoning was maximum 24% (n=24) in 20-29 year group followed by 30-39 year group 22% (n=22), 40-49 and 50-59 years were 15% (n=15) and the least was with 0-9 years and 70-79 years 3% (n=3).

Table 4: Categorization based on domicile.

SL.NO	Domicile	No. of patients (n=100)	Percentage (%)
1	Rural	90	90
2	Urban	6	6
3	Sub urban	4	4

Out of 100 patients, people from rural area were predominant 90% (n=90) followed by urban 6% (n=6) and the least was with sub urban 4% (n=4).

Table 5: Educational status of the patients (n=100).

SL. No	Education	No. of patients (n=100)	Percentage (%)
1	Primary Care	40	40
2	High School	26	26
3	Graduate	25	25
4	Post Graduate	9	9

Literacy status of the cases showed that 40% (n=40) had primary education, 26% (n=26) had high school education 25% (n=25) were graduates and 9% (n=9) were post graduates.

Table 6: Poisoning cases based on marital status.

SL.NO	Marital status	No. of patient (n=100)	
		Males	Females
1	Married	43	14
2	Unmarried	21	12
3	Widow	1	5
4	Divorced	1	3

The marital status of the cases showed that number of married people were more 57% (n=57) as compared to unmarried 33% (n=33). It was followed by widow 6% (n=6) and finally divorced 4% (n=4).

Table 7: Occupational status of the patients.

SL.NO	Occupational status	Number of Patients (n=100)	Percentage (%)
1	Student	31	31
2	Farmer	28	28
3	Housewives	16	16
4	Labor	13	13
5	Business	12	12

The occupation details of patients showed that students 31% (n=31) were more prone for poisoning, followed by farmers 28% (n=28), housewives 16% (n=16), labor 13% (n=13) and the least by businessmen 12% (n=12).

Table 8: Manner of poisoning.

SL.NO	Manner of poisoning	Number of patients (n=100)	Percentage (%)
1	Suicidal	89	89
2	Accidental	11	11

Out of the 100 cases 89% (n=89) were suicidal in nature and 11% (n=11) were accidental.

Table 9: Interval prior to the hospital admission.

Interval prior to the hospital admission	Number of patients(n=100)	Percentage (%)
<3 hrs	55	55
6-12 hrs	37	37
Undetermined	8	8

The time which elapsed between the poison intake and the start of treatment varied from 0-12 hrs and maximum number of patients reached hospital within 3 hrs 55% (n=55) followed by 6-12 hrs 37% (n=37) and the time of admission of 8% (n=8) were undetermined.

Table 10: Nature of organophosphorous compound.

SL.NO	Name of compound	Number of patients (n=100)	Percentage (%)
1	Cypermethrin+Chlorpyriphos	23	23
2	Unknown	22	22
3	Monocrotophos	20	20
4	Ethyl Parathion	11	11
5	Methyl Parathion	9	9
6	Malathion	6	6
7	Chlorpyriphos	6	6
8	Cypermethrin+Propentos	1	1
9	Glyphosphate	1	1
10	Diazinon	1	1

It was observed in our study that highest number of patients consumed Cypermethrin+Chlorpyriphos 23% (n=23) followed by Unknown OP compound 22% (n=22), Monocrotophos 20% (n=20), Ethyl Parathion 11% (n=11), Methyl Parathion 9% (n=9). Chlorpyriphos and Malathion accounted for 6% (n=6) of poisoning and the least consumed compounds were Diazinon, Cypermethrin + Propentos and Glyphosphate 1% (n=1).

Table 11: Poison category according to WHO.

SL.NO	Class of compound	Number of patients	Percentage (%)
1	Chlorothiophos	50	50
2	Ethyl Parathion	11	11
3	Methyl Parathion	9	9
4	Malathion	6	6

5	Diazinon	1	1
6	Tenephos	1	1

As per the study Chlorthiophos 50% (n=50) accounted for more poisoning followed by Ethyl Parathion 11% (n=11), Methyl Parathion 9% (n=9), Malathion 6% (n=6) and the least consumed compound was Diazinon and Tenephos 1% (n=1).

Table 12: Complications of patients.

SL.NO	Complications	Number(n=100)	Percentage (%)
1	Intermediate syndrome	42	42
2	Cardio respiratory	26	26
3	Not specified	23	23
4	Others	9	9

Most common complication observed in our study was intermediate syndrome 42% (n=42) followed by cardio respiratory 26% (n=26), not specified 23% (n=23) and others (includes burns, aspirational pneumonia, ulcers around mouth and other GI complications) were 9% (n=9).

Table 13: Severity of poisoning as per Glasgow Coma Scale.

SL.NO	GCS	Number (n=100)
1	3-8	43
2	9-12	44
3	13-15	13

Out of the 100 cases majority of the cases had the score 9-12 44% (n=44) followed by 3-8 43% (n=43) and in 13-15 there were only 13% (n=13) of people. This revealed that most of them had moderate brain injury.

Table 14: Symptoms presented by patients.

SL.NO	Symptoms	Percentage (%)
1	Abdominal Cramp	0.31%
2	Abdominal Pain	1.55%
3	Burn	2.17%
4	Cough	5.90%
5	Convulsion	0.62%
6	Drowsy	6.52%
7	General Weakness	8.07%
8	Headache	0.93%
9	Intermediate Syndrome	0.93%
10	Loss Of Consciousness	10.25%
11	Less Oxygen Saturation	0.93%
12	Loose Stool	11.49%
13	Neck Muscle Weakness	1.86%
14	Pupil Dilation	0.62%
15	Respiratory	15.84%
16	Secretions	0.31%
17	Up rolling of Eyes	0.62%
18	Vomiting	31.06%

As per our study the most predominant symptom shown by the patients who consumed poison was vomiting 31.06% followed by respiratory problems 15%, loose stools 11.49%, loss of consciousness 10.25%, general weakness 8.07% and the least symptoms observed was secretions and abdominal cramp 0.31%.

DISCUSSION

Organophosphorous compounds also known as “cholinesterase inhibitors” are widely used compounds in the form of pesticides. Exposure to organophosphorous can be accidental or suicidal in nature.

Acute OP compound poisoning is one of the commonest cause of poisoning in India. The use of OP pesticides is widespread in developing countries for increasing the yield of agriculture products. The scenario is not much different in India. Easy availability and low cost plays a major role in both accidental and suicidal poisoning.

As per the reports WHO estimates that three million cases of pesticide poisoning occur worldwide every year, with 220,000 deaths, most of which are intentional. Because of the easy and unrestricted availability of insecticides especially OP compounds this has become the easiest choice for suicidal attempts.

Our study was conducted in a tertiary care hospital. During our study period a total of 100 cases were enrolled and we categorized our cases into different classes based on the type of OP compound used, age, sex, socio-economic status, education, domicile, marital status and occupation.

In our study male preponderance 66% (n=66) were observed with respect to females. These may be due to the fact that males were more exposed to stress, strain and occupational hazards compared to females.

Out of the 100 cases most of them 24% (n=24) belonged to the age group 21-29years followed by 30-39years 22% (n=22), 40-59years 15% (n=15) 10-19years 10% (n=10), 60-69years 8% (n=8) and the least in older age and in children 3% (n=3). This could be due to the reasons that this age group was more prone to work pressure, love failure, marital problems, quarrel with family other life settlement factors etc.

Based on socio-economic status lower class people 50% (n=50) consumed more amount of poison followed by middle class 36% (n=36) and the least was with high class 14% (n=14).

People belonging to rural population 90% (n=90) consumed highest number of poison than urban 6% (n=6) and suburban 4% (n=4) which was similar to a study conducted by Yogesh G et al at a tertiary care hospital in Hyderabad Karnataka region.

In our study it was found that poisoning was more prevalent among the people who have received primary care basis 40% (n=40) followed by high school 26% (n=26), graduates 25% (n=25) and post graduates 9% (n=9). Primary care was more vulnerable to poisoning which may be due to the fact that they are under continuous financial crisis and day to day stressful life. This was similar to the study conducted by Abubakar et al at KIMS Bangalore.

Marital status of the victims reveals that married males 43% (n=43) were more prone to poisoning than married females 14% (n=14). The pattern was similar on considering unmarried group. Unmarried males consumed more amount of poison 21% (n=21) than unmarried females 12% (n=12). The above results coincide with that of the study that Karki et al conducted in a tertiary care hospital in Nepal.

Occupation details showed that students 31% (n=31) were more prone for poisoning. This was due to the inability to achieve the targets on professional, educational and socio-economic sectors. These was followed by farmers 28% (n=28), housewives 16% (n=16), labor 13% (n=13) and finally business 12% (n=12).

Most of the cases 89% (n=89) were suicidal in nature and 11% (n=11) were accidental. The most common risk factors identified were mental illness, mood swings of youth and pressure from cultural and social backgrounds.

As per the study most of the victims 55% (n=55) were brought to the hospital within three hours of attempt. 37% (n=37) were brought to the hospital within 6-12 hours and 8% (n=8) were undetermined.

In the present study the most common OP compound abused was chlordiophos 50% (n=50). As agriculture is the main occupation of the people in this area and chlordiophos is the commonly used pesticide in this locality, most cases were caused by chlordiophos, this is evident from other studies conducted in South India.

In our study it was found that nearly 42% (n=42) of people had intermediate syndrome followed by cardio-respiratory arrest 26% (n=26) and 23% (n=23) were not specified.

As per Glasgow Coma Scale of the victims 44% (n=44) had moderate brain injury followed by mild brain injury 43% (n=43) and 13% (n=13) had severe brain injury. [1], [2], [4], [6], [8], [9], [11], [12], [14]

CONCLUSION

Poisoning is the most preferable method of self-harm. Pattern and magnitude of poisoning demands a multi-sectorial-approach for facing this problem. Organophosphorous poisoning is a medical emergency. Organophosphorous pesticide poisoning was the most common method of self-harm and thus identifies a positive relationship between impulsive suicidal behaviour and availability of pesticides in the region. Most of the poisoning cases were noted among students. The reason for poisoning was mainly relayed on the inability to achieve the targets on professional, educational and socio-economic sector which cannot be treated medically. . This study describes the importance of patient counselling and essentiality of poison information center in hospitals. We as clinical pharmacists can implement various poison prevention strategies at various levels and thus can reduce the complications, morbidity and mortality associated with it. Various strategies involve:

- Authentication of pesticide act, so that import, manufacture, sale, transport, distribution and use of pesticides could be regulated.
- Provide additional information to the existing data on pesticides in all aspects.
- Poison Information Centre should be created in each hospitals for immediate diagnosis and treatment.
- All the hospitals should have separate toxicological unit which deals with clinical poisoning cases.
- Persons with psychosocial problems should be identified and must be referred for psychiatric counseling.
- Regular counseling programmes in school as well as at college level by a well-trained faculty.

Even though the study portrait that patient counselling and poison control center are the vital sectors to be concentrated by the clinical pharmacists, further research is necessary to confirm this.

ABBREVIATIONS

SL.NO	ABBREVIATIONS	DETAILS
01	OP	Organophosphorous Compound
02	PIC	Poison Information Center
03	WHO	World Health Organization
04	ICU	Intensive Care Unit
05	COPD	Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease
06	DM	Diabetes Mellitus
07	HTN	Hypertension

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

We would like to show our deepest gratitude to our guide Dr. Gloria. K. Sam, other teaching staffs of Bapuji Pharmacy College, our beloved parents, seniors and classmates for their strong contributions and support for fulfilling our study.

CONFLICT OF INTERESTS

None

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